

Electronic Spectra of Mixed Halocobaltates (II) in Acetonitrile and Nitromethane

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A few mixed trihalo-, tetrahalo- and pentahalocobaltates(II) have been isolated and characterized by us¹⁻³ and their electronic spectral study in nujol mull has also been reported^{4,5}. Now we are reporting the solution spectra of mixed tetra- and pentahalocobaltates(II).

Experimental

The mixed tetra- and pentahalocobaltates(II) were prepared according to the methods reported earlier^{2,6}. A Unicam SP700 spectrophotometer was used for recording the spectra in visible and near i. r. regions in acetonitrile and nitromethane solutions. BDH grade acetonitrile was purified by the method of Walden and Birr⁶ which consisted in repeated distillation over phosphorus pentoxide till the dehydrating agent no longer turned yellow, followed by distillation over anhydrous potassium carbonate to remove traces of P₂O₅ and final distillation without any drying agent. BDH grade nitromethane was purified by drying P₂O₅ and fractional distillation, the fraction distilled at 101 was collected.

1 cm matched silica cells were used to hold the solution and solvent. Higher concentrations had to be used for recording the spectrum in the near i. r. region than in the visible region. For comparison purpose diffuse reflectance spectra of these compounds were also recorded using MgO as reference.

Results and Discussion

Mixed Tetrahalo Cobaltates(II): It has been observed that the effect of low symmetry in the case of mixed tetrahalocobaltates(II) [C₂v for (CoX₂Y₂)²⁻] as compared to simple tetrahalocobaltates(II) (Td for CoX₄²⁻) on the electronic spectra (in nujol mull) is not significant and, in fact, ligand field parameters for the former have been calculated using equations applicable to tetrahedral symmetry⁶.

The centres of gravity of γ_3 bands in acetonitrile, nitromethane and diffuse reflectance and of γ_2 bands in acetonitrile** are reported in Table I and are two representative spectra in the visible region are shown in Fig. 1. It is clear from the

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of

- (a) [(C₂H₅)₄N]₂[CoCl₄];
- (b) [(C₂H₅)₄N]₂[CoCl₂Br₂];
- (c) [(C₂H₅)₄N]₂[CoCl₄] + (C₂H₅)₄NCl (1 : 1) in acetonitrile

Table I that for any particular compound the γ_3 band in solution has moved to higher energy compared to that in solid (diffuse reflectance) which indicates that the solvent molecules must be replacing one or more halides from the coordination sphere, thus still retaining the tetrahedral geometry but moving the band to higher energy side due to higher position of the solvent molecule in the spectrochemical series. The hypothesis of solvent coordination was confirmed by the observation of red shift in the γ_3 and γ_2 bands of a mixture of (C₂H₅)₄N₂CoCl₄ and (C₂H₅)₄NCl in acetonitrile as compared to those of [(C₂H₅)₄N]₂CoCl₄ alone (Table I).

A peculiar phenomenon in the acetonitrile solution spectra is that while γ_3 values are in the

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** γ_2 bands could not be recorded in full in nitromethane and diffuse reflectance.

TABLE I— γ_2 AND γ_3 TRANSITIONS IN HALOCOBLTATES(II)

$$B=(nC_4H_9)_4N^+; E=(C_2H_5)_4N^+; M=(CH_3)_4N^+$$

Compound	$\gamma_2(\text{cm}^{-1})$ (Aceto- nitrile)	$\gamma_3(\text{cm}^{-1})$ (Aceto- nitrile)	$\gamma_3(\text{cm}^{-1})$ Reflec- tance	$\gamma_3(\text{cm}^{-1})$ (OH_2NO_2)
$M_2(\text{CoCl}_4)$	15385	5236	15150	15267
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_4)$	15314	5263	—	15150
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{Br}_2)$	15198	5348	14749 ¹	15106
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{I}_2)$	14970	5464	14388 ¹	14925
$E_2(\text{CoBr}_2\text{I}_2)$	14535	5495	13889	15106
$M_2(\text{CoBr}_4)$	14815	5291	14493	14815
$M_2(\text{CoCl}_6)$	15270	5291	15267	15267
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_6)$	15150	5208	15198	15106
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_4\text{Br}_2)$	15340	5291	14925	—
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{Br}_2)$	15270	5291	14815	15198
$M_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{Br}_2)$	15150	5376	14993	15106
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{Br}_2)$	15040	5348	14641	15038
$M_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{Br}_3)$	15340	5361	14641	15038
$E_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{Br}_4)$	15200	5348	14706	15150
$M_2(\text{CoBr}_2)$	14815	5291	14600	14706
$B_2(\text{CoCl}_2\text{I}_2)^*$	15200	—	14430	15198
$E_2(\text{CoBr}_2\text{I}_2)^*$	14600	—	13986	14600
Equimolecular Mixture of $E_2(\text{CoCl}_4) + \text{ECl}$	15150	5208	—	15106

* γ_2 bands were not observed fully.

expected order, that is, $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{I}^-$, γ_2 values are reverse of the expected order (Table I); this may be attributed to high absorption by the solvent in the near i. r. region or possibly the solvent interacts with the complex ion in some other way than simple coordination.

Mixed Pentahalocobaltates(II): We have concluded from the electronic spectral (nujol mull) and far i. r. studies³ that the mixed pentahalocobaltates(II), in fact, are double salts containing tetrahedral cobalt e. g., $(\text{CoCl}_4\text{Br})^{3-}$ is $(\text{CoCl}_3\text{Br})^{2-}\text{Cl}^-$. The solution is similar to that in Cs_3CoCl_5 which has been shown to be $\text{Cs}_2\text{CoCl}_4.\text{CsCl}$ by crystallography⁸. The γ_3 values for the mixed pentahalocobaltates(II) are nearly the same as for the corresponding mixed tetrahalcobaltates(II) and they also show a similar trend (Table I). This supports the assumption that similar ions are present in the solution of both the halocobaltates(II).

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Preparation and Characterisation of μ -Dihydroxotetrakis(Salicylato)-Diaquodichromium(III)

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GILLARD¹ and coworkers have studied oxidative degradation mechanism of coordinated salicylic acid in form of *bis*(ethylenediamine)salicylato-cobalt(III) and have reported that the reactivity of salicylate is markedly modified by coordination. Complexes of cobalt(III) containing the bidentate salicylate ion undergoes reaction in which the organic moiety is modified while remaining bound to the metal ion. While trying to extend the study to other salicylate complexes, it was found that the salicylate complexes of many metals including those of transition metals have been reported by a number of workers²⁻⁵ but most of these studies have been carried out in solution. In this paper we report the preparation and characterisation of μ -dihydroxotetrakis(salicylato)diaquodichromium(III) by analysis, derivatographic study, i.r. spectra, magnetic susceptibility measurements, U.V. and visible reflectance spectra. Lastly the oxidation of the complex was carried out in 12 N sulphuric acid medium.

The instruments used and method of preparation of the complex have been described earlier^{6,7}. The percentages of chromium were determined volumetrically⁸. C and H were estimated by element estimation technique. Complete analysis gives (Found Cr = 14.2%, C = 45.9%, H = 3.9%, calculated for $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ Cr = 14.4%, C = 46.45% and H = 3.7%). The stages of oxidation were followed potentiometrically⁹ using bright platinum electrode on a Chrompton potentiometer. The concentrations were so chosen that 10 ml of M/1120 μ -dihydroxotetrakis(salicylato)diaquodichromium(III) requires 10 ml of M/60 $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ for complete oxidation to CO_2 stage.

Derivatographic Study:

The combined D.T.G., D.T.A. and T.G.A. curve of a sample of 500 mg of the complex μ -dihydroxotetrakis(salicylato)diaquodichromium(III) was carried out with heating rate of 8°/min. The temperature was fixed between 30° to 800°. The summary of the results is tabulated in Table.

The first three products were confirmed by i.r. spectra, chemical tests and element estimation technique. The metal carbonate was confirmed by chemical tests and quantitative liberation of CO_2 . The final product was confirmed by powder X-ray analysis.